

Behaviour of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones towards action of POCl₃/DMF (Vilsmeier reagent) in presence of BF₃.Et₂O : a novel observation in the synthesis of chromones^ψ

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The influence of the presence of BF₃.Et₂O on the Vilsmeier reactions of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones and related naphthophenones has been examined. A significant and novel feature of this study is the development of new and facile procedure for the synthesis of some chromones. The reaction offers a first example of monoformylation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones.

There is considerable interest in the use of Vilsmeier-Haack reagent (POCl₃/DMF, also known as Vilsmeier reagent) for formylation of aromatic, heteroaromatic and non-aromatic compounds^{1,2}. When applied to RCOCH₃ type of compounds, such as acetophenone, etc., Vilsmeier reaction leads to the synthesis of β-chlorovinylaldehyde derivatives. But in case of 2,2-difluoro-4-methylnaphtho-1,3,2-dioxaborin compounds, double formylation occurs³. Nohara *et al.* explained these results on the basis of prohibition of enolisation by 1,3,2-dioxaborin ring formation allowing double formylation. Following this strategy, they carried out double formylation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone derivatives to afford 3-formylchromones (Scheme 1)⁴.

Scheme 1

They proposed that in case of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, *o*-hydroxy group forms hydrogen bonding with COCH₃ group similar to dioxaborin ring system. But no supporting evidences were provided.

In contrast to these observations, in a related work by Bass, *o*-hydroxyacetophenones were reported to afford isoflavones and chromones on treatment with BF₃.Et₂O and MeSO₂Cl/DMF⁵.

These observations, coupled with our interest in the synthesis of chromone derivatives needed for I^{III} mediated oxi-

dation reactions, led us to investigate the behaviour of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and its various derivatives towards action of POCl₃/DMF in presence of BF₃.Et₂O.

Results and discussion

Initially, we chose the compound 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone (**1a**) because of our interest in 7-hydroxychromones. Thus **1a** was treated with BF₃.Et₂O followed by Vilsmeier reagent (POCl₃/DMF). The reaction, however, did not give any 7-hydroxy-3-formylchromone. Instead, the product obtained from this reaction was identified as 7-hydroxychromone **2a** (on the basis of m.p. and spectral analyses) in 55% yield (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

This novel observation prompted us to investigate the effect of substituent(s) towards this reaction. Accordingly, several *o*-hydroxyacetophenones **1b-i** were subjected to reaction with Vilsmeier reagent in presence of BF₃.Et₂O. However, Vilsmeier reaction of these *o*-hydroxyacetophenones did not follow the similar trend. For example, 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (**1b**), 4-chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone (**1c**) and 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone

^ψDedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji for his outstanding contribution to this Department.

(1d) underwent smooth transformation to the corresponding chromones **2b-d**. On the other hand, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (**1e**), did not yield the expected chromone. Instead, the only product obtained from this reaction was found to be the dimer **3e** (Scheme 3). Similar results were obtained from the $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ induced Vilsmeier reaction of 5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone (**1f**) and 5-bromo-2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone (**1g**).

It is to be noted that the formation of similar dimeric products have been reported earlier by Nohara *et al.* in the Vilsmeier reaction of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone. However, the mechanistic pathways for the formation of these dimers are not certain. Further work in this connection is under progress.

Scheme 3

In the case of 2-acetyl-1-naphthol (**1h**), similar treatment yielded corresponding 3-formylchromone **4a** together with unreacted starting material (Scheme 4). The same trend was followed by 1-acetyl-2-naphthol (**1i**). The condensa-

Scheme 4

tion of 3-formylchromone and unreacted starting material in these cases is likely to get prevented due to bulk of naphthyl molecules. Results of the present study are summarized in Table 1.

Finally, the most striking and significant feature of this investigation is that $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ induced Vilsmeier reaction offers a first example of chromones synthesis involving monoforylation in certain *o*-hydroxyacetophenones.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. ^1H NMR spectra of the compounds were recorded on Bruker-300 MHz instrument in CDCl_3 .

o-Hydroxyacetophenones **1** needed for the present study were synthesized by Fries migration of their respective phenyl acetates, which in turn, were prepared from corresponding phenols as reported in the literature⁶.

General procedure for Vilsmeier reaction of o-hydroxyacetophenones :

To a solution of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone **1** (1 equiva-

Table 1. Results of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ induced Vilsmeier reaction of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones **1**

Starting materials	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	Products	Yield (%) [*]	m.p.(°C)	Lit.m.p. ⁷ (°C)	Solvent ^{**}
1a	H	OH	H	H	2a	55	210–212	218 ^a	A/B
1b	H	H	Cl	H	2b	52	138–139	140–142 ^a	A
1c	H	Cl	Me	H	2c	45	166–167 (decomp.)	171–173 ^a (decomp.)	A
1d	H	H	OH	H	2d	41	238–239	243–244 ^a	A
1e	H	H	H	H	3e	53	170–171	173–174 ^b	C
1f	H	H	Me	H	3f	50	189–190	192–193 ^b	A
1g	H	OH	Br	H	3g	37	170–172 (decomp.)	–	B
1h	-benzo-		H	H	4h	48	160	160–161 ^a	D
1i	H	H	-benzo-		4i	51	192–194	195–196 ^a	D

^{*}Yield (%) of the products was calculated with respect to their corresponding *o*-hydroxyacetophenone.

^{**}Solvent of recrystallisation : A; ethyl alcohol, B; acetone, C; methyl alcohol, D; column chromatographic separation by using pet. ether-ethyl acetate as eluent.

-Spectral data of all the products were in full agreement.

lent) in dimethylformamide (DMF), was added 3 equivalents of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ under dry conditions. To the resulting solution, Vilsmeier reagent [prepared separately by dissolving POCl_3 (1 equivalent) in DMF] was added at temperature of $50\text{--}60^\circ$ and the mixture was allowed to stir at the same temperature for 2–3 h. Then, the reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice. Solid separated was filtered and dried. Finally, the crude product so obtained was purified either through recrystallisation or by column chromatography.

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